

Open & Transparent Research Practices

Case Study – Architecture (Architecture, Built Environment & Planning)

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Introduction

Openness and transparency constitute a foundational principle for research integrity, as set out in the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity. Openness can promote rigour, constructive scrutiny, accountability and can enable others to build on research. However, it can also bring challenges. Critically, what openness and transparency can and should mean varies across disciplines and fields of study. This is one of a series of case studies in a wide range of disciplines that illustrate these differences. The series is intended to enable researchers to see similarities and differences between fields, and to inform those supporting open research through, for example, training, policies or incentives. This case study is from the field of Architecture, the Built Environment & Planning. It is based on a single interview with a researcher, and is therefore illustrative rather than representative.

Background

The field of Architecture concerns the art, process and technique of planning, designing and constructing structures, from those with a specific commercial or industrial function, to habitable buildings and spaces. These structures are elements of the Built Environment, which also includes transportation links, energy and utilities systems, recreational spaces, and more. A growing part of the sector is the design and management of the sustainable built environment, helping to reduce its energy consumption and general environmental impact.

The interviewee is a Senior Research Fellow, with a background in building science and architecture. They are part of a university group who perform revenue-generating research and consultancy around sustainable buildings, energy and environmental policy, and the impacts of climate change on the built environment. Research projects have included carbon footprinting, thermal/acoustic surveys, renewable energy studies, and much more.

These projects are generally short, fast response pieces, and their outputs are diverse: reports, analyses, white papers, and assessment tools are produced, alongside, less commonly, peer-reviewed papers. Research partners are also varied, including county councils, the Ministry of Defence, and NHS trusts, as well as other private organisations, such as builders and developers, and manufacturing companies.

Relevance of openness & transparency

When conducting research for clients and partner organisations, a focus of the interviewee is ensuring that any data and the manipulation methodology developed are described as openly and transparently as possible. Reasons for this extend beyond client understanding: these final reports are often made publicly available by the clients themselves.

Available and accessible source data is another important aspect of openness. This is often published by the UK Government or other academics, and utilised heavily by the interviewee, for example, when producing carbon emission calculations for the local council.

However, despite being open and available, it is still important to reference this source data explicitly, and be clear as to when and where this data is used during the research process. The data manipulation methodology should also be described explicitly, as well as the conditions and limitations of the final outputs generated. Finally, the communication of these should be well-considered: a careful lay summary can help explain detailed topics to those with differing backgrounds. Without these elements, analysis can run the risk of becoming “black-box,” or far less explainable, both to clients and the general public.

The nature of the research undertaken by the interviewee affects the openness of the final outputs. Projects are generally “rapid-response,” and delivered on timescales that discourage publication of results in peer-reviewed journals, a process that can take months to years. Openness is achieved in other ways: as mentioned, final reports, tools (including data dashboards) and analyses are often published by clients, where they can be scrutinised by those interested. This is more common with clients that are subject to the Freedom of Information Act, such as local councils and other public services.

Pros and cons of openness & transparency

Increased openness and transparency in the interviewee’s research improve its credibility. When detailed information regarding data and analysis methodology can be made open, project outputs can be interrogated and better understood by clients. This is especially important where analysis is complex, for example, in the quantification of carbon emissions from business supply chains. In addition, making these elements open allows the replication of calculations, helping to improve trust in the research.

This increased scrutiny, from clients, the general public, and journalists, can lead to the identification of errors, or methodological differences in opinion. If these are large, their identification might carry a significant reputational risk. If small and more easily addressed, their identification can help improve the overall research quality, in a process similar to more formal peer-review. Ultimately though, the increased interest and engagement from clients and the general public (if released) that comes with open and transparent research is seen as a large benefit, especially if large topics, such as the climate emergency, are to be addressed effectively.

Making all research elements open is not always possible, and doing so could breach legal or license agreements. This is often in relation to data, and intellectual property. Input source data can sometimes only be made open with explicit permission from the data owners. Output data produced might also be embargoed, for example, when working on high-security projects, such as defence contracts.

Finally, there is a clear time cost to making research open and transparent, due to the additional work required in making outputs sufficiently detailed, but still clear and accessible. If recipients/the general public don’t engage with these outputs, this can feel like wasted effort. Alternative strategies are sometimes employed, where individuals can follow-up and request more detail via email, if interest is judged to be low.

Wider context & trends

Generally, the interviewee feels that their research landscape is becoming more open, even though theirs is in a less traditional academic setting. There is more of an expectation to be open and transparent with research, especially from local councils. This has been facilitated by technological developments, such as the ability to rapidly create interactive websites and dashboards. This leads to far greater engagement with, and longevity of, for example, research related to carbon footprints of counties, which would have previously remained in static reports. However, with so much data being published, new challenges are faced, such

as creating impactful research that cuts through the background noise, whilst ensuring that published data is up-to-date and current.

Engagement and interest in certain research topics follow economic and political cycles, which creates upward pressure on research openness. In the interviewee's field, research is generally related to the usage, price and availability of energy. With councils declaring climate emergencies, energy prices soaring, and through actions from groups such as Extinction Rebellion, there is an extremely high level of interest in research related to the climate, encouraging the publication of any reports and analysis related to this. With research aligned to the public interest, it becomes far easier to be open and transparent, even for projects closer to the consultancy end of the spectrum.

The openness of the interviewee's research is still important, even if their outputs are not published in peer-reviewed journals. Their group still aims to provide technical, rigorous outputs, following themes of open research as much as possible. However, pressures to be more or less open are then heavily influenced by clients, much more so than in "typical" research projects. As a result, there might be more limited control over the level of openness available for researchers, who must be mindful of client requirements.

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